

**A STRATEGIC MODEL FOR BUILDING COMPETITIVE ADVANTAGE IN
PRIVATE ISLAMIC SECONDARY SCHOOLS IN SERANG CITY
(A Multi-site Analysis of SMPIT Al Izzah and SMP Nuur El Bantany in Serang City)**

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ABSTRACT

This study aims to identify the implementation of competitive advantage strategies, analyse internal school factors and external environmental pressures, and formulate a competitive advantage strategy model in private Islamic schools. The study employs a qualitative approach with a multi-site comparative design. Data were analysed using thematic interactive analysis supported by NVivo 12 software and SWOT analysis. Research data were obtained from subjects and informants consisting of headteachers, deputy headteachers for curriculum, teachers, students, school committees, and parents. Data collection techniques included in-depth interviews, observation, and documentation. The findings indicate that private Islamic schools have implemented strategic management in a practical and sustainable manner, in which competitive advantage strategies are developed through a hybrid approach. Schools do not adopt a single strategy in isolation; instead, they combine strategies contextually according to internal capacities and external pressures. Private Islamic schools are able to survive and grow not because they are free from constraints, but because they are capable of managing these limitations strategically. Further findings describe a continuous process within private Islamic schools that results in cost affordability, value-based differentiation, community loyalty, stability in student enrolment, and increased public trust. Another key finding, which can be interpreted within the competitive advantage strategy model, suggests that the sustainability of competitive advantage is determined not only by academic excellence but also by relational strength and social legitimacy. The proposed model demonstrates that private Islamic schools are able to build a strong competitive position through the integration of values, strategy, and operational implementation, whilst emphasising strategic flexibility as a key factor in their competitiveness. The contribution of this study lies in the development of a model that is both conceptual and applicable. Efforts to build competitive advantage do not rely on

a single strategy, but rather on a combination of cost leadership, differentiation, and focus strategies.

Keywords: Strategy Model, Competitive Advantage, Private Islamic Junior High Schools

Introduction

Islamic education in the reform era has been revitalised following the fall of the New Order. During the reform era, the education system remained centralised, which hindered educational institutions from developing and being creative (Tilaar, 2002).

Over the past few decades, the education system has undergone a significant restructuring process, shifting from a conventional educational management approach towards a strategic management model that is more focused on a vision for the future (Blanco, 2013). Consequently, the application of strategic management in the field of education is regarded as crucial for strengthening the competitive advantage of educational institutions. The inability of educational institutions to achieve this excellence necessitates concrete action, one of which is through the implementation of efficient management strategies.

Strategic management in education is closely linked to the creation of a learning environment that supports continuous learning (Stukalina, 2010). Strategic management acts as a key driver in developing innovative programmes in the education sector, with a focus on human resource management. In her research, Baltabayeva states that the implementation of strategic management can reduce risks within educational organisations and transform them into new, profitable opportunities (Baltabayeva et al., 2020). The implementation of strategic management in educational institutions is considered capable of making a significant contribution to the institution's progress. This method offers guidance in addressing existing challenges whilst capitalising on available opportunities, both currently and in the future. Furthermore, strategic management also facilitates more accurate decision-making and the implementation of more efficient policies (Mappasiara, 2018).

Strategic management in Islamic education is now of crucial importance, given the gradual erosion of Islamic values in everyday life. The growing influence of foreign cultures has led to a decline in Indonesian culture, particularly in matters of worship. Strategic management in the context of Islamic education is carried out through a series of stages, including strategic formulation, strategic planning, programme development, and budgeting. These four processes of strategic management in Islamic education must be carried out carefully and systematically to achieve optimal results. Strategic management requires a leader capable of coordinating their team to ensure they remain on the agreed planning path (Shava et al., 2021).

Given the increasing challenges and threats faced by Islamic educational institutions, it is essential to manage education professionally through strategic

management that can lead these institutions towards excellence, rather than merely survival. The proliferation of educational institutions without adequate management tends to lead to stagnation, where such institutions merely survive without any impetus to innovate or renew themselves. Educational administrators, such as headteachers and heads of education departments as modern executives, must possess the ability to observe and respond to various challenges arising from the external environment, both near and far. The immediate external environment refers to the context that has a direct impact on the operations of educational institutions. This encompasses the various potentials and conditions within the education sector that form the institution's primary focus, competitive dynamics, and the circumstances of education consumers and graduate users. All these factors will have implications for the formulation of strategies deemed effective in supporting Islamic educational institutions to achieve their objectives. The distant external environment encompasses a variety of forces and conditions arising beyond the immediate external environment, including socio-economic conditions, politics, national security, technological developments, and global challenges. These implicitly influence the implementation of the education system within a school institution (Yunus, 2016).

Data from Worldtop20.org for 2024 shows that, out of 203 countries worldwide, Indonesia's education ranking stands at 67th place, on a par with Albania in 66th place and Serbia in 68th place (International Education Database, 2024). Worldtop20.org is a website that regularly publishes global education rankings, including through the World Top 20 Education Poll programme, which regularly surveys the 20 best education systems across 203 countries.

The Indonesian Central Statistics Agency recorded in 2023 that the number of schools in Indonesia for the 2022/2023 academic year stood at 399,376, an increase of 1.18% from the previous academic year, which recorded 394,708 schools. There were 93,385 nursery schools (TK), 94.67% of which were private. In addition, the Ministry of Religious Affairs manages 31,049 *raudatul athfal* (RA) units. At primary level, there are 148,975 primary schools (SD) and 26,503 madrasah ibtidaiyah (MI), with 93.54% of MI being private schools.

There are 41,986 lower secondary schools (SMP), of which 56.83% are state-run. There are 19,150 madrasah tsanawiyah (MTs), 92.03% of which are private junior secondary schools. At the senior secondary level, there are 14,236 senior secondary schools (SMA) and 14,265 vocational secondary schools (SMK). Madrasah aliyah (MA) number 9,827, with 91.75% of these being state-run. Overall, the educational level with the highest number of institutions in Indonesia is primary school. The majority of educational institutions such as nursery schools, MI, MT, SMA, SMK, and MA are managed by the private sector (Nurhasinah, 2023).

Table 1.1
Number of Schools in Indonesia for the 2022/2023 Academic Year

No.	School	Total
1.	Nursery Schools (TK)	93,385
2.	Raudhatul Athfal (RA)	31,049
3.	Primary School (SD)	148,975
4.	Primary Madrasah (MI)	26,503
5.	Lower Secondary School (SMP)	41,986
6.	Junior High School	19,150
7.	Upper Secondary School (SMA)	14,236
8.	Vocational High School (SMK)	14,265
9.	Senior Islamic School (MA)	9,827
TOTAL		399,376

Source: Indonesia Statistical Report 2023

Islamic educational institutions play a vital role in supporting the continuity of education in Indonesia, particularly in the regular and sustainable improvement of Islamic education (Arifin, 1991). Those responsible for organising Islamic education must have the courage to offer alternative solutions to address various educational challenges.

Measures that can be taken include improving quality, maintaining a competitive edge, and striving to meet the expectations and needs of the community. The presence of high-quality Islamic educational institutions at various levels is eagerly awaited by the Muslim community; indeed, such institutions are now regarded as an urgent necessity. This situation indirectly requires the administrators of Islamic institutions to adopt a more rational approach and to work hard to meet the expectations of the wider community.

Indonesia continues to strive to achieve optimal educational standards, despite facing various challenges at all levels of education. One key challenge is encouraging public participation in accessing high-quality higher education services. (Muzaki, 2023)

The challenges facing the education sector are also being felt by private educational institutions in Serang City. According to data from Banten Raya, in 2024, eight private junior high schools in Serang City have closed down (Baldan, 2025); four of the eight schools that have closed are Islamic schools, meaning that the number of private schools in Serang City has fallen from 62 to 54. Of the 54 private junior high schools in Serang City, 26 have fewer than 60 pupils from Year 7 to Year 9 (Serang, 2025). This is below the minimum threshold set by the Ministry of Primary and Secondary Education, which is 20 pupils per class.

Given that almost half of private junior high schools have fewer than 60 pupils and that eight of these private schools have closed, this indicates that private junior high

schools in Serang City remain under-resourced and are far from ideal as educational institutions. In the SPMB (new student admission system), some schools rely solely on students who have not been accepted by state junior high schools, as private schools lack specific strengths and advantages, making them an unattractive option for prospective students. Furthermore, regarding school operations, the majority of private junior high schools in Serang City rely solely on BOS (School Operational Costs) funding; naturally, this is insufficient to cover the school's numerous needs, whether in terms of human resources such as salaries, facilities and infrastructure for learning, or other requirements.

SMP IT Al Izzah and SMP Nuur El Bantany are two lower secondary schools in Serang City that have proven *resilient* in the face of various challenges and obstacles, as evidenced by their consistent student numbers year on year; they possess distinctive *values* and are among the most popular lower secondary schools in Serang City.

SMP IT Al Izzah, with its combination of the National Curriculum, JSIT (Integrated Islamic Schools Network) and BPI (Islamic Personal Development), makes Al Izzah a school with a curriculum that emphasises not only competence but also student character, complemented by a wide range of achievements at sub-district, city, provincial, national and international levels.

Al Izzah has become one of the '*role model*' schools designated by the Serang City Education Department; it has received various awards, including as an 'Adiwiyata' school, a 'Penggerak' school, a 'Healthy School', a 'Child-Friendly School', and has even been designated a 'population preparedness school'.

The school employs high-quality teachers who hold national certifications, and places a strong emphasis on fostering academic excellence; indeed, the school actively supports the preparation for various competitions and academic Olympiads.

Al-Izzah Integrated Islamic Junior High School aims to be a leading school where pupils can compete with other junior high schools and strive to build a positive image and achieve outstanding results. Al-Izzah Integrated Islamic Junior High School serves as a nurturing environment for the Muslim generation, constantly striving to foster a generation that is of high quality, diligent, and devout in their worship, as well as capable of rising to the challenges of the times as they evolve.

Nuur El Bantany Junior High School is also a private Islamic school of a fairly high standard; it is an A-accredited school (excellent) by the National Education Quality Assurance Agency (BPMP), combining the national curriculum with that of a modern Islamic boarding school. It offers specialised programmes, including *a bilingual approach* integrating Arabic and English into daily conversation, in-depth study of classical Islamic texts (*turots*), and the development of *life skills* among its pupils.

SMP Nuur El Bantany, located in the Sayabulu area of Cipocok subdistrict in Serang City, has won numerous awards at subdistrict, city, provincial and even national levels. The facilities and infrastructure at SMP Nuur El Bantany are quite adequate, with

admission fees and tuition fees that are reasonably affordable—and in some cases even waived—despite the school being a *boarding* school. Furthermore, a selective recruitment process ensures that the teaching staff are of a very high standard. The environment is disciplined, and all pupils are required to live in the boarding house; study times are scheduled and supervised by *a supervisor*, keeping them away from distractions such as gadgets, TV and the outside environment. A culture of healthy competition amongst pupils also drives academic achievement.

A school with a competitive advantage is one that can foster loyalty among its stakeholders (Ermaya, 2020) . Bashori (2017) emphasises that there are two key principles that an organisation or educational institution must master in order to achieve a competitive advantage, namely from the customer’s perspective and unique educational services. Competitive advantage in educational institutions can take the form of innovation, creativity, and educational quality that will serve as a benchmark for the community. Furthermore, the utilisation of differentiated flagship programmes capable of offering varied and high-quality education. Based on preliminary observations, the researcher found that there are a number of factors that enable SMP IT Al Izzah and SMP Nur El Bantany to fulfil the main principles outlined by (Bashori, 2017) , leading the researcher to select these two schools as the subjects of the study, specifically focusing on how to build competitive advantage in private Islamic schools in the city of Serang.

Competitive excellence in Islamic educational institutions cannot be overlooked; indeed, Muslims are encouraged to compete in doing good, provided that such competition is conducted in a proper manner and does not involve intrigue or cheating. Allah, *exalted be He*, says in Surah Al-Muthaffifin, verse 26:

وَفِي ذَلِكَ فَلْيَتَنَافَسِ الْمُتَنَافِسُونَ

“And in that let those who compete, compete.”

According to Quraish Shihab(1996) , in his commentary on Surah Al-Muthaffifin, verse 26, he states that the word فَلْيَتَنَافَسِ derives from the word *nafis*, which refers to something of great value, such that its possession becomes the object of competition and requires serious effort to attain. Furthermore, Quraish Shihab explains that the Quran has, since ancient times, emphasised the importance of competition in meeting life’s necessities. This can be traced back to Prophet Adam, the first human to set foot on earth. Prophet Adam was reminded by Allah *Subhanahu Wa Ta’ala* that life on earth differs from that in Paradise, where various luxurious amenities are available. On earth, to meet one’s needs, effort and hard work are required first.

High-quality schools are closely linked to the development of outstanding human resources. Schools of high quality should ideally be able to produce high-quality educational inputs, processes and outputs. Increasingly fierce competition in the world

of education demands that every school think more creatively, innovatively, and responsively in maintaining and developing its quality. One strategic step that can be taken is to implement strategic management in school administration to improve the overall quality of education (Komarudin et al., 2022).

Previous research indicates that many educational institutions have not yet fully implemented strategic management effectively. This gap is evident in a lack of understanding regarding the importance of strategic planning and continuous evaluation in achieving educational objectives (Hidayat & Setyaningbudi, 2024).

This study is important for highlighting how Islamic junior secondary schools can develop strategies to build competitive advantage. By analysing strategic management practices at Al Izzah and Nour El Bantany, this research aims to identify the key factors contributing to their success in addressing challenges and capitalising on existing opportunities. Furthermore, this research will also provide recommendations for other educational institutions to improve their strategic management.

The primary objective of this study is to develop a strategic framework or model that can be adopted by private Islamic junior high schools in order to enhance their competitive advantage. As such, this study will not only contribute to the development of educational management theory but also to educational practice within the community. It is hoped that the results of this study will serve as a reference for decision-makers in educational institutions in formulating effective and efficient strategies to achieve better educational outcomes (Nalendro Ikhsan Sandityo & Muafi, 2024).

Through a multi-site analysis of Al Izzah and Nour El Bantany in Serang City, this study will explore best practices in strategic management that can be adopted by other Islamic junior secondary schools. This study will also consider external factors influencing the performance of educational institutions, such as government policies, technological developments, and the ever-changing needs of society. By understanding this context, it is hoped that this study can provide more precise and practical recommendations for a strategic model to build competitive advantage in Islamic junior high schools.

Research Methodology

This study focuses on the development of a strategic model for building competitive advantage in private Islamic junior high schools, by conducting a comparative analysis between SMP IT Al Izzah and SMP IT Nour El Bantany in Serang City, using a qualitative approach. Qualitative research is a type of research conducted in natural settings (Sugiyono, 2013). Bogdan and Taylor, as cited by Moleong, explain that qualitative research methods are procedures that generate descriptive data in the form of written or spoken words from individuals and actors observed in the context of their daily lives (Moleong, 2000). In this study, the researcher applied a

phenomenological qualitative research method with a multi-site design, and conducted the analysis using an inductive approach. Descriptive research is characterised by explaining and analysing available data, such as situations experienced, existing relationships, activities, observable views and attitudes, or ongoing processes, as well as interrelated influences. This study can be categorised as field research.

The approach adopted is a phenomenological one, which aims to understand the phenomena occurring within the research subjects. This study employs a multi-site design that focuses intensively and in detail on several institutions.

The research design employed by the researchers here is a multi-site research design, which is often defined as a design encompassing more than a single site. This means that if the research involves more than one location, then it employs a multi-site design. A multi-site design has a number of advantages and disadvantages that need to be considered when compared to a single-site design. Evidence from a multi-site study is considered more convincing, and the research as a whole is considered more robust. The researcher decided to use a multi-site research design, with the aim of ensuring that each site under investigation could be explored optimally, thereby hopefully yielding valid research findings in line with the researcher's expectations.

The researcher applied a phenomenological paradigm through a qualitative approach to gain a comprehensive, in-depth and holistic understanding of this study. Data were collected in the natural setting as the primary data source. This study aims to uncover phenomena and symptoms through an in-depth approach, as well as to identify a comprehensive and holistic model of competitive advantage strategies at Al Izzah Islamic Junior High School and Nuur El Bantany Junior High School (SMP) in Serang City. The researcher will continue the analysis not only on substantive findings relevant to the research focus but also on formal aspects.

This study employs a qualitative method with a multi-site comparative design, using SWOT analysis as a strategic mapping framework; this method is frequently used and implemented by researchers in the social sciences, including the field of education. The concept of a multi-case study is an empirical investigation that explores phenomena within a real-life context, where the boundaries between phenomena and context are not clearly defined and where various sources of evidence are utilised (Yin, 2018) . A multi-site study is research conducted through an intensive, in-depth, detailed, and comprehensive examination of a case.

Results and Discussion

Strategic Management as an Internalised Value Practice in Private Islamic Schools

The primary novelty of this study lies in the finding that strategic management in private Islamic schools is not positioned as a formal planning document, but rather as a practice of values internalised within the day-to-day management of the school . Unlike many previous studies which emphasise strategic management as an administrative

instrument, this study demonstrates that strategy is embedded in operational decisions, organisational culture, and the school's social relations. Strategy becomes a dynamic process that is continually adapted to the Islamic vision, the needs of the students, and the demands of society. This finding broadens the perspective of strategic management within the context of Islamic education. Thus, this novelty offers a more contextual and practical understanding of strategy.

This approach demonstrates that competitive advantage is not built through rigid long-term planning, but rather through the consistency of value-based managerial practices. Strategy is not merely a direction, but becomes the organisation's way of thinking and acting. This enriches the literature on educational management, which has hitherto tended to place strategy at a structural level. This study affirms that the internalisation of values is the key to the success of strategy in private Islamic schools.

The Hybrid Model of Porter's Generic Strategies in the Context of Private Islamic Schools

The second novelty lies in the finding that private Islamic schools do not apply Porter's generic strategies in isolation, but rather in a contextual hybrid form. SMPIT Al Izzah and SMP Nur El Bantany simultaneously combine cost leadership, differentiation, and focus strategies in accordance with their respective capacities and social environments. This finding differs from Porter's classical assumption, which tends to strictly separate these three strategies. In the context of private Islamic education, hybrid strategies are, in fact, a rational and adaptive choice.

This research demonstrates that cost-effectiveness can coexist with value-based differentiation and distinctive services. Market focus does not limit innovation but rather strengthens the school's social relevance. Consequently, this novelty enriches competitive strategy theory with a perspective grounded in value-based education and social mission. These findings simultaneously challenge the view that hybrid strategies risk diminishing competitive advantage.

Cost Leadership Based on Social Accessibility, Not Merely Financial Efficiency

The third novelty of this study lies in the reinterpretation of cost leadership strategy within the context of private Islamic schools. Cost leadership is not merely interpreted as a focus on operational costs, but as a social strategy to expand access to education. SMP Nur El Bantany demonstrates that budgetary efficiency is implemented to ensure affordability for lower-middle-income communities. Meanwhile, SMPIT Al Izzah integrates cost efficiency with investment in systems and technology.

These findings expand the concept of cost leadership to include ethical and social dimensions. The low-cost strategy is not positioned as price competition, but rather as '—a form of social responsibility for educational institutions. Thus, this

novelty offers a more humanistic and contextual framework for cost leadership. This concept is relevant for value-based private schools with a public service mission.

Differentiation Based on Islamic Values as a Source of Social Legitimacy

The fourth innovation lies in the finding that the differentiation of private Islamic schools is built not primarily through physical facilities, but through the integration of Islamic values across all organisational dimensions. Religious values are not merely curriculum content, but also shape school culture, teacher-student relationships, and communication with parents. This value-based differentiation generates strong social legitimacy in the eyes of the community.

This finding enriches the concept of differentiation in educational management by incorporating symbolic and cultural dimensions. Competitive advantage is not measured solely through academic output, but through social trust and acceptance. Thus, this novelty demonstrates that values can function as strategic assets. This is rarely discussed in depth in studies of private school competitive advantage.

Focus Strategy as a Mechanism for Sustainability, Not a Constraint on Growth

The fifth novelty of this research lies in the interpretation of the focus strategy as a tool for maintaining the school's sustainability, rather than merely a restriction on market segments. SMP Nur El Bantany consciously concentrates its services on a specific segment of society to maintain quality and stability. Meanwhile, SMPIT Al Izzah implements focus through the strengthening of systems and reputation, albeit with a broader scope of segmentation.

These findings demonstrate that focus strategies can be flexible and adaptive. Focus does not necessarily imply exclusivity, but rather strategic selectivity. This novelty offers a fresh perspective on how focus strategies operate within value-based educational organisations. It enriches our understanding of focus strategies in the non-profit and semi-commercial sectors.

Competitive Advantage as the Result of Alignment Between Values, Strategy, and Practice

The sixth novelty lies in the conceptualisation of competitive advantage as the result of alignment between values, strategy, and managerial practices. This research demonstrates that the competitive advantage of private Islamic schools is sustainable when there is harmony between the Islamic vision, strategic policies, and operational implementation. A lack of synchronisation between these three elements has the potential to weaken the school's competitiveness.

These findings yield a theoretical contribution in the form of a value-alignment-based competitive advantage model. This model differs from purely ' ' competitive approaches that emphasise resources and market position. Thus, this novelty enriches

strategic management theory with normative and contextual dimensions. This model is relevant for Islamic educational institutions and other value-based organisations.

Methodological Contribution through Context-Based Multi-Site Analysis

The seventh novelty lies in the multi-site analytical approach, which captures strategic variations and similarities within their respective contexts. By comparing SMPIT Al Izzah and SMP Nuur El Bantany, this study demonstrates that there is no single universal strategic model. Competitive advantage is built through adaptation to the local social, economic, and cultural context.

This approach makes a methodological contribution by strengthening cross-case analysis as a means of reconstructing substantive propositions. These findings underscore the importance of context in educational management studies. Thus, the novelty of the research lies not only in the results but also in the way of understanding and interpreting Islamic educational strategies more deeply.

Conclusion

Based on the research findings regarding competitive advantage strategies at SMP Al Izzah and SMP Nuur El Bantany in Serang City, the following conclusions can be drawn:

Both schools implement strategic management that is practical and sustainable, where strategies are not positioned as administrative documents but rather as operational guidelines for day-to-day school management. Strategies are designed adaptively, taking into account the institutional vision, the needs of students, and community expectations. Competitive advantage strategies are built through a hybrid approach, namely a combination of cost leadership, differentiation, and focus. Cost leadership is realised through budgetary efficiency and resource optimisation, differentiation through the strengthening of integrated Islamic education, and focus through intensive services for segments of the community that share compatible values. Islamic values form the core of the differentiation strategy, not only in the curriculum but also in organisational culture, character development, and teacher–pupil and school–parent relationships. Religious values serve as a source of social legitimacy as well as the primary distinguishing factor compared to other schools. The service strategy is positioned as a key element of competitive advantage, placing students and parents at the centre of the service. Regular communication, parental involvement, and family-school partnerships are crucial strategies in building community trust and loyalty. Digital technology is utilised strategically to support administrative efficiency, communication, and learning, enabling the school to enhance service quality despite resource constraints.

The internal factors (IFAS) that constitute the main strengths of both schools include a commitment to Islamic values, a strong work culture, teacher dedication,

organisational flexibility, and the ability to integrate the academic and Islamic curricula. These strengths form the primary foundation for building differentiation and public trust. The internal weaknesses faced are relatively similar, namely limited resources, a limited number of permanent teachers, and high teacher workload. However, the research findings indicate that these weaknesses do not constitute major obstacles as they are addressed through strategies of efficiency, teamwork, and adaptive dual roles. Significant external factors (EFAS) include increasing competition between schools, changing parental preferences, the socio-economic conditions of the community, and the growing demand for higher educational quality. These factors drive schools to continue innovating without compromising their core values. Key external opportunities arise from growing public trust in integrated Islamic education, the need for character-based education, and support from digital technology. Meanwhile, threats stem from price competition, demands for service quality, and increasingly complex public expectations. The interaction between internal and external factors indicates that the competitive advantage of private Islamic schools is contextual, heavily influenced by the school's ability to interpret its environment and adapt its strategies to the social conditions of the surrounding community.

The resulting strategic model demonstrates that the competitive advantage of private Islamic schools is built through the integration of three key elements: the socio-economic context of the community, Islamic values as a strategic foundation, and the implementation of adaptive generic strategies. The model positions Islamic values and an integrated Islamic vision as the central axis guiding all strategic decisions, ranging from academic planning, human resource management, services, to the utilisation of technology. Generic strategies are operationalised through four implementation areas—academic, human resources, services, and technology—which are interconnected and mutually reinforcing. These four areas serve as the primary instruments in achieving tangible competitive advantage. The model also emphasises that internal weaknesses are not eliminated but managed strategically through efficiency, programme prioritisation, and the strengthening of collective commitment. Consequently, the resulting competitive advantage is realistic and sustainable. Overall, the formulated strategic model demonstrates that the competitive advantage of SMP IT Al Izzah and SMP Islam Nur El Bantany is value-based, adaptable to the environment, and socially accepted, thereby ensuring the long-term stability of students, affordability, and public trust.

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